

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PULTRUDED FIBER

REINFORCED NYLON 6 COMPOSITES (I)

CHEN-CHI M. MA and MENG-SONG YN
INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING
NATIONAL TSING HUA UNIVERSITY
HSIN-CHU, TAIWAN, 30043 CHINA

ABSTRACT

The feasibility study of the pultrusion of fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites from ϵ -caprolactam monomer has been conducted by a proprietary method. Fiber reinforcements investigated include glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar[®] 49 aramid fiber.

It was found that the mechanical and thermal properties of unidirectional fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites (i.e. tensile, flexural, impact strength and HDT, etc.) increase with the increasing of fiber content. Experimental results of tensile strength agree with the rule of mixture except carbon fiber/Nylon 6 composites which show some deviations due to fiber breakage. Kevlar[®] fiber / Nylon 6 composites possess the highest notched Izod impact strength and specific tensile strength, while carbon fiber/Nylon 6 composites show the highest tensile strength, flexural strength and specific flexural strength.

Key Words: Pultrusion, glass fiber, carbon fiber, Kevlar[®] fiber, Nylon 6 composites.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion is an automatic and continuous process for fabricating fiber reinforced plastics. The annual growth rate of this process is about 17-20%(1) in the past decade. Pultruded product is received widespread applications in sporting goods, corrosion resistant parts, architecture, transportation, agriculture, chemical engineering, electronic and electrical engineering, aircraft and aerospace, etc.

Various resins and fiber reinforcements have been used in pultrusion process, however, the major systems are glass fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester (UP) composite (2), glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (EP) composites (3-5). The resins used most are thermoset resins (e.g. UP, EP, etc.).

However, thermoplastic pultruded composites possess the following advantages: higher degree of processing freedom (reformability, repairability and good welding ability), faster production rate, good toughness, scrap can be reused and free from solvent pollution problem. Hence, researches using thermoplastic pultrusion are developing recently (6-10). This study was conducted to investigate the feasibility study of Nylon 6 pultrusion from ϵ -caprolactam monomer and to evaluate the properties of pultruded glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar® fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials:

- (a) Glass fiber roving: RS-240 (E-Glass), filament diameter is 13.1 μm , tensile strength is 2.24×10^5 psi, density is 2.54 g/cm³, Nittobo Co., Japan.
- (b) Carbon fiber roving: HTA-12000, filament diameter is 7 μm , tensile strength is 5.26×10^5 psi, density is 1.77 g/cm³, Toho Co., Japan.
- (c) Kevlar® fiber roving: Kevlar 49, filament diameter is 11.9 μm , tensile strength is 4.0×10^5 psi, density is 1.45 g/cm³, DuPont Co., U.S.A.
- (d) ϵ -caprolactam: China Petrochemicals Developing Co., Taiwan, China.
- (e) Adipic acid: extra pure, Merck Co., Germany.
- (f) Nylon 6: synthesized in this study.

2. Instruments:

- (a) Pultrusion machine: A pultrusion die with multiple heating zones. Dimensions of die are 82 x 1.27 x 0.208 cm, self-designed.
- (b) Universal material testing machine: (1) Instron 1123, Instron Co., U.S.A. and (2) HT-8501, Horng Dar Co., Taiwan, China.
- (c) Impact strength testing machine: TMI-43-1, Testing Machine Inc., U.S.A.

3. Property Measurements:

- (a) Tensile strength: ASTM D-3039, sample dimensions are 22.9 x 1.25 x 0.20 cm, crosshead speed is 2.5 cm/min.
- (b) Flexural strength: ASTM D-790, sample dimensions are 12.7 x 1.25 x 0.20 cm. span is 9 cm, crosshead speed is 2 mm/min
- (c) Notched Izod impact strength: ASTM D-256, sample dimensions

are 6.35 x 1.25 x 0.20 cm.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to investigate the effect of type and content of fiber on the properties of pultruded Nylon 6 composites, glass fiber (GF), carbon fiber (CF) and Kevlar® fiber (KF) reinforced Nylon 6 (NY) composites (GF/NY, CF/NY, KF/NY, respectively) with various fiber content were fabricated in this study. Tensile strength, flexural strength, and notched Izod impact strength of composites were measured.

1. Tensile strength and specific tensile strength:

Figure 1 illustrates tensile strengths of pultruded glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar® fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites with various fiber volume contents. Results indicate that tensile strength increases with the increasing of fiber volume content and a linear relationship existed. Table 1 shows the deviations of experimental and theoretical tensile strength of pultruded fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites where theoretical data are predicted by the rule of mixture of composite. Experimental results of tensile strength agree with the rule of mixture except carbon fiber/ Nylon 6 composites which show some deviations which might be due to fiber breakage during processing.

The effect of fiber volume content on specific tensile strength is shown in Figure 2. The specific tensile strength of KF/NY is the highest while that of GF/NY is the lowest among the composites studied. CF/NY shows the highest tensile strength. Density of KF/NY is 1.22-1.28 g/cm³, CF/NY is 1.38-1.43 g/cm³, GF/NY is 1.72-1.89 g/cm³, respectively.

2. Flexural strength and specific flexural strength:

The effect of fiber volume content on flexural strength is illustrated in Figure 3. Flexural strength was measured by using compressive destruction at the center loading point, this leads to debonding between fibers and resin. The higher the fiber volume content, the higher the flexural strength. The order of flexural strength is CF/NY > GF/NY > KF/NY. The effect of fiber volume content on specific flexural strength is presented in Figure 4. The order of KF/NY and GF/NY is the reverse of that of flexural strength.

3. Notched Izod impact strength:

Figure 5 illustrates notched Izod impact strength versus fiber volume content of pultruded glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar® fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites. Impact strength increases with the increasing of fiber volume content is explicit. KF/NY possess the highest impact strength, while CF/NY is the lowest. The increasing of impact strength of fiber rein-

forced composite is mainly due to the resistance of fiber to crack propagation(11). Hence, the higher the fiber content, the higher the impact strength.

4. Properties comparison of pultruded fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites with other pultruded composites:

Tables 2 and 3 show the properties comparison among pultruded glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites and other pultruded thermoplastic composites (ABS and PPS) and thermoset composites (Unsaturated Polyester, Phenolic and Epoxy). Properties comparison are summarized as following:

(a)Tensile strength: the pultruded GF/NY fabricated in this study possess the highest tensile strength among five pultruded glass fiber reinforced composites.CF/NY shows the highest tensile strength besides CF/Epoxy.

(b)Flexural strength: both GF/PPS and CF/PPS have the highest flexural strength among all pultruded composites, however, both GF/NY and CF/NY are somewhat lower in flexural strength.

(c)Notched Izod impact strength: the impact strength of GF/NY is higher than that of the GF/UP. CF/NY and CF/PPS show about the same impact strength.

5. The effect of pultrusion rate on the mechanical properties of composites:

Pulling rate of pultrusion determines the production rate of a pultrusion process.Hence, a proper pulling rate will optimize the mechanical properties and production rate. Figure 6 shows the effect of pulling rate on the flexural strength and HDT of pultruded Kevlar® fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites. Generally, the lower the pulling rate, the higher the flexural strength and the better surface of pultruded part. For a lower pulling rate the resident wetting time of fiber in resin bath will be longer,hence the wet-out of fiber will be better. An optimum pulling rate, 60-90 cm/min. was found in this study.

IV.CONCLUSIONS

In this research, the feasibility of the proprietary pultrusion of glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites has been demonstrated. The optimum pulling rate is between 60-90 cm/min.This study shows that the higher the fiber volume content, the better the properties (tensile strength,flexural strength and impact strength) of pultruded parts. Among the three pultruded composite investigated in this study, CF/NY shows the highest tensile strength, flexural strength and specific flexural strength, while KF/NY possess the highest impact strength and specific tensile strength. Pultruded fiber reinforced Nylon 6 composites explicit excellent tensile strength and impact

strength compare to pultruded thermosetting composites.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the National Science Council, Taiwan, China, under the contract NO. NSC 78-0405-E007-07 .

VI. REFERENCES

1. Chiou-Rong Jeng, Jih-Shun Hwang, UCL Chemical Information Journal, Taiwan, China, p.4-13 Aug., (1987).
2. Robert Adolph Florentine, 37th Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 10-B, Sheraton, Washington, U.S.A. (1982).
3. J.A. Kershaw, 38th Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 6-C, Houston, Texas, U.S.A. (1983).
4. R.A.P. Spencer, Advances in Pultrusion of Carbon Fiber Composites, International Conference on Carbon Fiber, 21, The Plastics Institute, London, U.K., Feb. (1974).
5. Jin-Shun Hwang, Master Thesis, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan, China (1986).
6. Ronald C. Hawley, Polymer Composites Inc., Wicono, Minn., U.S. Patent 4,439,387 (1984).
7. A. Madenjian, N. Tessier, N. Schott, 40th Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 11-F, Atlanta, Georgia, U.S.A. (1985).
8. Aaron Sternfield, Modern Plast., p.36-38 Jan. (1987).
9. Jame E. O'Connor and William H. Beever, 42th Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 1-D, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S.A. (1987).
10. J.S. Hwang, S.N. Tong, S.J. Tsai, Paul H.H. Hsu, Pater T.K. Wu, 43rd Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 6-E, Cincinnati, Ohio, U.S.A. (1988).
11. Long-Sheng Chiou, Master Thesis, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan, China (1984).
12. Lawrence E. Nielsen, "Mechanical Properties of Polymers and Composites", p.483, Marcel Dekker, Inc. N.Y. (1974).
13. John Theberge, Jane Crosby and Marygail Hutchins, 40th Annu. Conf. RP/C, SPI, 4-C, Atlanta, Georgia, U.S.A. (1985).
14. Wen-Chang Shih, Master Thesis, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan, China (1987).
15. "Advanced Composites", Bulletin of Phillips Petroleum Company U.S.A. (1986).

FIG. 1. TENSILE STRENGTH VS. FIBER VOLUME CONTENT OF PULTRUDED GLASS FIBER (O), CARBON FIBER (□) AND KEVLAR® FIBER (Δ) REINFORCED NYLON 6 COMPOSITES.

FIG. 2. SPECIFIC TENSILE STRENGTH VS. FIBER VOLUME CONTENT OF PULTRUDED GLASS FIBER (O), CARBON FIBER (□) AND KEVLAR® FIBER (Δ) REINFORCED NYLON 6 COMPOSITES.

FIG. 3. FLEXURAL STRENGTH VS. FIBER VOLUME CONTENT OF PULTRUDED GLASS FIBER (O), CARBON FIBER (□) AND KEVLAR® FIBER (Δ) REINFORCED NYLON 6 COMPOSITES.

9. D. J. Blundell and B. N. Osborn , Polymer , 24, 953 (1983).

Table 1. Rate Constant, K , obtained from Avrami Equation at $T_c = 280^\circ\text{C}$ and 180°C for PEEK/C.F.Composites with various carbon fiber contents.

C.F.Content % Wt.	0	25	41	60
K at $T_c = 280^\circ\text{C}$	0.0210	0.0174	0.0145	0.0110
K at $T_c = 180^\circ\text{C}$	0.1620	0.1510	0.1020	0.0721

Fig. 1. DSC thermograms of PEEK neat resin crystallized at various temperatures.

Fig. 4. DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite crystallized at various temperatures. (fiber content 60wt)

Fig. 2. DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite crystallized at various temperatures. (fiber content 60wt)

Fig. 3. DSC thermograms of PEEK neat resin crystallized at various temperatures.